

Leveraging LLMs for Smart Cities Qualitative Data Analysis

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Abstract. Public authorities frequently conduct surveys and analyse data from citizens, a process that is often labour-intensive when performed manually. This paper explores how Generative Artificial Intelligence (GAI) can assist in automating data analysis for public authorities. In this respect, we investigate the potential of Large Language Models (LLMs) to perform sentiment analysis and summarisation of unstructured data as smart services. Using data from the East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood (EBLN) as a case study, we assess the accuracy and precision of these models and validate the results against ground truth data and expert evaluations. Our findings indicate that sentiment classification achieved over 90% accuracy. In contrast, the expert validation rated the summarisation without context accuracy highly satisfactory, however, the satisfaction was low when contextual summarisation was evaluated. These results suggest that LLMs offer a promising approach to improving the efficiency of qualitative analysis, though further research is required to enhance their accuracy and usefulness.

Keywords: sentiment analysis, text summarisation, smart cities, generative Artificial Intelligence.

1 Introduction

Cities are undergoing significant transformations as they seek to harness the full potential of urban governance driven by Information and Communication Technology[1]. Several benefits are sought to manage the complexity of urban systems and gain insights from public participation in planning processes [6,18]. An important driving force in this transformation concerns the information overload from urban systems and local initiatives such as citizen observatories. The recent policy shift towards more emphasis on citizen engagement in data gathering, planning and decision-making

processes e.g., European Bauhaus¹, Built4People² and EU Mission Cities³, requires further technological support to manage and analyse such data. In particular, much of the data is gathered through surveys or comments provided by citizens on specific plans or topics via social media or other participation platforms. Since these data are typically unstructured, analysing it can be time-consuming and requires specific skills. This problem can be exacerbated by the growing number of surveys and high levels of public participation.

Over the past decade, data analytics has emerged as an important innovative technology in the domain of smart cities [1, 22]. Various statistical, machine learning and data mining techniques have proven to be revolutionary in the context of Smart City Data Analytics. Among these, deep learning models have become one of the most cutting-edge technologies, offering significant contributions across a range of applications for smart city services [15, 26].

Recently, disruptive technologies such as Generative Artificial Intelligence (GAI) and Large Language Models (LLMs) are revolutionising the way data analysis can be performed. Their benefits cut across domains such as transportation, urban planning, and smart buildings. Their ability to analyse and evaluate unstructured qualitative data with high accuracy and precision makes them ideal candidates to help public authorities streamline their processes. In this respect, we investigate the suitability of LLMs for two automated services for public authorities: (i) sentiment analysis and (ii) summarisation for survey data. We applied selected models to real, unstructured textual data collected through the East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood (EBLN)⁴ initiative in Bristol, United Kingdom. The EBLN is one of the pilots under the Horizon Europe GREENGAGE project⁵. The GREENGAGE project aims to develop citizen observatories to facilitate European GREEN Deal policy objectives across different pilots in EU and UK. By leveraging citizen science, the project will collect extensive unstructured qualitative data through surveys, discussions and comments gathered through the GREENGAGE GREEN Engine, such as mobile apps. Additionally, the project will combine sensor data from traffic monitoring and pollution levels, with citizens' feedback to raise public awareness and engagement in environmental issues, as well as to gather their opinions and needs on these topics.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents background information on LLMs and their suitability for data analysis tasks. Section 3 introduces the EBLN dataset, detailing our pre-processing steps, model architectures, and experimental design of the two key services: sentiment analysis and text summarisation. We discuss our findings and their implications in Section 4, followed by conclusive remarks in Section 5.

¹ https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/about/about-initiative_en

² <https://built4people.eu/>

³ <https://netzerocities.eu/mission-cities/>

⁴ <https://eastbristolliveableneighbourhoods.commonplace.is/>

⁵ <https://www.greengage-project.eu/>

2 Background

2.1 Large Language Models for Qualitative Analytics

Traditional approaches to qualitative data analysis rely on understanding vast amounts of unstructured data (text, video, or audio) through manual processes [8]. These approaches typically require significant time investments, and are heavily dependent on human expertise, inevitably incorporating individual biases into the analytical process.

The rise of Large Language Models has encouraged a shift towards developing more sophisticated, automated systems for qualitative data analysis. These LLMs, comprising billions of parameters and trained on vast datasets, have demonstrated remarkable capabilities in various language processing tasks [16]. Various studies have explored the application of LLMs in qualitative analysis, focusing on specific tasks such as sentiment analysis [13], text summarisation [2,27], theory-driven categorisation [25], or holistic solutions [19,23]. However, it remains a gap in understanding their practical benefits in real-world scenarios. Current research often lacks evaluation from end-users, or applications in real smart cities case studies. This study aims to address this gap by applying LLMs on recent survey data, and incorporating feedback from actual practitioners. Our final goal is to set the foundation for future research directions, and assess the true potential of LLMs in qualitative data analysis within practical contexts.

2.2 Zero-shot learning and LLMs

Training machine learning models is a resource-intensive task, requiring substantial data, time, and computational power [20]. However, real-world scenarios often impose limitations on these resources. Zero-shot learning is a machine learning paradigm that enables models to make predictions for classes they have not encountered during training [3], reducing computational costs and the need for large amounts of annotated datasets. While this has been in the past mainly used for computer vision, it has recently gained attraction with the surge of LLMs [24].

LLMs are pre-trained on vast amounts of data, capable of performing a wide range of language tasks effectively. Zero-shot learning leverages this extensive knowledge base, making LLMs flexible and adaptable across various scenarios. Given the ability of LLMs to understand and generate human-like text, LLMs can be directed to perform zero-shot learning simply through natural language instructions or ‘prompts’ [14]. This conversational manner of task description allows these models to adapt to new contexts without the need for task-specific training data, time-consuming data preparation steps or extensive model fine-tuning. Moreover, this approach is particularly beneficial in providing non-experts with a tool to perform language analysis.

In this study, we have created suitable prompts to perform zero-shot learning for sentiment classification and summarisation. Creating effective prompts involves a trial-and-error approach, which can be challenging [17]. While exploring the nuances of prompt creation is outside the scope of this initial study, we will focus on discussing the results obtained. It is important to note that varying prompts may yield different results in this context.

2.3 Sentiment Classification using LLMs

Understanding public opinion, citizens' experiences and satisfaction is crucial in the context of Smart Cities. This enables authorities to assess initiative reception, pinpoint concerns, improve quality of life, and ensure responsive governance. To accomplish these objectives effectively, sentiment classification emerges as an invaluable analytical tool [7]. This natural language processing technique aims to determine the emotional tone or attitude expressed in a piece of text. It typically involves categorising text into binary sentiments - positive or negative - although more nuanced classifications are also feasible.

Traditional sentiment classification techniques often rely on lexicon-based methods, which use predefined dictionaries of sentiment-bearing words, or machine learning approaches such as Naive Bayes, Support Vector Machines and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) which learn from labelled data [21]. These techniques, while effective, can struggle with context-dependent sentiments, require large amounts of labelled data for training, demand extensive feature engineering and dataset preparation, which can be time-consuming and costly to perform. In contrast, LLMs excel in understanding context and nuanced language, require minimal task-specific training due to their pre-trained nature, and can perform well with limited or no labelled data [13,21]. LLMs' versatility in processing sentiments across a range of domains, with superior accuracy, makes them ideal for sentiment analysis, especially in the context of survey data collection, characterised by large quantitative of unstructured data covering different topics.

2.4 Flan-T5: model selected for sentiment classification

For the sentiment classification task in this study, we have tested Flan-T5 language model, developed by Google AI in 2022 [4]. Flan-T5 is an open-source, improved version of the original T5 (Text-to-Text Transfer Transformer) model, treating all natural language processing tasks as text-to-text problems. This model has been fine-tuned on a diverse range of tasks using instruction-based learning, making it suitable to be used in zero-shot learning context. This versatile approach adapts well to sentiment classification, with the model's instruction following ability making it an easy tool for language analysis, even for non-technical users. Flan-T5 is comparable in performance to many heavyweight, proprietary models while being open-source [28], reducing cost constraints and allowing customisation. These features make it an excellent candidate for this investigation, balancing advanced capabilities, flexibility, and cost-effectiveness. Google has released multiple variants of Flan-T5, ranging from compact models with 80 million parameters and 300MB in size, to expansive versions with 11 billion parameters requiring 80GB of memory. For this study, we evaluated the following checkpoints available on Hugging Face⁶:

1. Flan-T5-small: 80 million parameters, 300MB
2. Flan-T5-base: 250 million parameters, 990MB

⁶ https://huggingface.co/docs/transformers/main/en/model\char'_doc/flan-t5

3. Flan-T5-large: 780 million parameters, 1GB

The choice of these model sizes was motivated by the aim to assess the performance on common laptops with limited resources, evaluate the trade-off between execution time and accuracy across different model sizes, and make the approach accessible to a wide range of users.

2.5 Summarisation using LLMs

In the digital age, where information is abundant and readily available, the ability to condense and summarise text is of high importance. Text summarisation serves as a powerful tool that aids in the efficient extraction and comprehension of key information from large volumes of data. It enables individuals and businesses to sift through vast amounts of content and quickly identify the most relevant and critical information. By transforming lengthy documents into concise summaries, it saves time, enhances productivity, and supports informed decision-making processes. As such, text summarisation plays a crucial role in navigating information overload in today's data-driven world.

Text summarisation approaches have been around for a while. For example, frequency-based, graph-based and topic-based approaches aid in extractive summarisation techniques. On the other hand, Sequence-to-Sequence models such as RNNs and LSTMs aid abstractive summarisation. The emergence of LLMs promises to usher in a new era of summarisation techniques. However, being relatively recent, not much work has been performed to investigate the performance of LLMs for summarisation in various domains. Although there is limited research, it suggests that traditional approaches still perform reasonably well for generic tasks, though LLMs might outperform them when fine-tuned for specific domains [9,10]. Therefore, in this paper, we explore how LLMs perform in summarisation of survey data.

2.6 Llama3: model selected for summarisation

For the summarisation service, we have chosen the Llama3 models. This model has been recently released by Meta in 8B and 70B parameter scales in both instruction-tuned and fine-tuned varieties⁷. We opted to test Llama3 because it is a new model that has shown promising results in various tasks, including summarisation, with comparable or superior performance to other leading LLMs.

The Llama3 models have been trained using a variety of techniques to optimise both the pretraining and post-training steps. In particular, a dataset containing 15 trillion tokens was specifically curated from publicly available sources to train the model. Rigorous quality control measures, including heuristic filters and eliminating semantic duplicates, have been implemented to improve data reliability compared to previous Llama versions. Taking into account these factors, along with the model's evaluation of 1,800 prompts across 12 essential tasks, including summarisation, we have selected

⁷ <https://ai.meta.com/blog/meta-llama-3/>

this model specifically for our data summarisation task with the aim to achieve robust, efficient, and practical summarisation results.

3 Methodology and Implementation

3.1 Case study and data collection

The East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood (EBLN) project is a community-driven initiative to transform East Bristol's streets. The main goal is to collaborate with local residents, workers, students and commuters to design streets that are liveable and people-friendly. This project is part of a co-design phase aimed at developing long-term solutions with the help of the local community. The EBLN is also a pilot in the Horizon Europe GREENGAGE project, which promotes inclusive citizen observatories by using digital solutions.

The survey data used in this study were collected between January and March 2022 by Bristol City Council, UK. Participants, including those living, working, or travelling to the area, shared their opinions either using an interactive online map⁸, or by engaging with members of Bristol City Council through door-to-door interviews or community discussions.

Face-to-face interviews were conducted and recorded manually. Citizens were asked about their thoughts on what they appreciate about their local area, and how they would like to improve it. They had the option to respond to either or both questions, resulting in over 400 individual contributions and a total of 845 comments of varying length. While the complete dataset cannot be disclosed due to confidentiality constraints, Table 1 presents a representative sample of responses collected.

Online, citizens could express their feedback by:

1. Marking specific locations on a map
2. Linking a feeling, chosen from a range of five sentiments, spanning from negative to positive, with the selected area
3. Providing optional comments in a free-text box
4. Additionally, selecting one or more topics related to their comments, reasons for their expressed feeling, and suggestions for improving the area

An example of response from the online survey is shown in Table 2. The dataset collected through the online tool comprises 540 geo-located entries, of which 90% contains both textual comments and sentiment labels. A preliminary study conducted on this dataset [5], which involved analysing the textual comments alongside the provided sentiment and topic labels, showed that most participants lived within the area and tended to emphasise negative aspects of their neighbourhood, particularly in relation to main roads and junctions. Interestingly, the word "road" frequently appeared in negative contexts, while "street" was associated with positive sentiments, reflecting nuanced perceptions of different urban spaces. Conversely, areas with green spaces generally

⁸ <https://eastbristolliveableneighbourhoods.commonplace.is/map/map>

received more positive feedback. Sentiment analysis showed that negative statements were more prevalent around safety and environment-related comments, while texts linked to community aspects displayed a more balanced distribution of sentiments.

Table 1. Example of responses from the EBLN interviews

Q1: What do you like about your local area?
A1: Good sense of community
A2: It's fairly diverse - there's a real sense of community, it feels very friendly
A3: Park, shops
Q2: How would you like to make it better?
A4: More activities for children and improve parks. Homes are too old and damaged and we need repairs
A5: Traffic
A6: Wider roads

Table 2. Example of responses from the online EBLN map.

Sentiment	Positive	Negative
Subjects	Trees and greenery on street, Street trees and planting	Walking, Crossings
Reasons	Pleasant	Not pedestrian friendly, Difficult to cross the street
Suggestions	Slow down traffic	Add crossing, Safer junction for walking and cycling
Comments	The street planters have reduced traffic speed and made the street 'greener'. Something similar could be done in other locations within the project area and in traffic displacement areas outside the project area	Hard to cross here - there is a traffic island slightly above this point but often want to cross lower down and it's hard to do so as the road is busy with two lanes of fast traffic.

The preliminary study [5] demonstrated the potential of analysing public feedback to inform urban planning initiatives. However, it also highlights the need for scalable and efficient methodologies. While the EBLN dataset has labelled textual data, most urban datasets lack such structured annotations, resulting in the need for extensive time to analyse and generate comprehensive summaries to extract insights and actionable steps.

In this study, we have tested our LLM-based methods against the EBLN datasets. For sentiment classification, we have focused on the online EBLN dataset, leveraging its pre-existing sentiment labels to assess our approach's accuracy and effectiveness. For the summarisation tasks, we have worked with both the online and in-person

collected data, and results have been evaluated by members of Bristol City Council directly involved in the EBLN and GREENGAGE project.

3.2 Data preprocessing

Our work centers exclusively on the free-text comments, and their corresponding sentiment labels in the case of the sentiment classification task, therefore all other features in our datasets were excluded. In line with our aim of utilising LLMs, our preprocessing was intentionally minimal. This is because LLMs are designed to handle natural language inputs, including variations in spelling, grammar, and informal expressions commonly found in public feedback. Therefore, for both tasks, we retained all comments regardless of length to preserve the full range of citizen feedback, since even brief comments can provide insight into urban perceptions.

For the summarisation tasks, two files were generated that included all the text comments. These comments were either placed in one column for the online dataset or in two columns for the two questions asked during the interviews. In the case of the sentiment classification task, we performed a sentiment simplification. The original dataset included five sentiment categories: positive, mostly positive, neutral, mostly negative, negative. Following the approach in [5] we have excluded the neutral comments, and grouped the remaining labels into two polar groups, positive and negative. We simplified the sentiments into binary classification to facilitate a clearer, more straightforward interpretation of public opinions, and avoid the complexities of neutral or fine-grained sentiment analysis, which demands more nuanced approaches. As a result of our preprocessing, our method was tested on 446 textual comments from the EBLN survey, with 52 comments labelled as positive.

3.3 Service 1: Sentiment Classification

For the sentiment classification task in this study, we have tested Flan-T5 language model in three different model sizes (see Section 2.4).

To provide a comprehensive comparison, we tested these models both on a laptop device with an Intel Core i5 processor, and on an NVIDIA Titan RTX GPU-equipped computer. This additional test helped us quantify the reduction in execution time achievable with more powerful hardware, providing insights into the scalability of our approach.

All the Flan-T5 model variants mentioned were tested using identical prompt instructions, to ensure a consistent and fair comparison across different model sizes. We aimed to use a clear and straightforward prompt, including only the essential components, namely the task name, task definition, and output format. Prompt format and wording were taken from [28].

Table 3. Sentiment classification prompt

```
Please perform Sentiment Classification task.

Given the sentence, assign a sentiment label from
['negative', 'positive'].
Return label only.

Sentence: {input_text} Label:
```

In the prompt, we specify the name of the task (Sentiment Classification), and provide instructions on the task itself (assign a label to a given sentence). We also specify the output format we require after the final word 'Label'. We have executed this prompt for every data point in the dataset, replacing {input_text} with the appropriate text content from the dataset.

3.4 Service 2: Summarisation

For the purposes of this use case, we used Llama 3 with 8 billion parameters, and ran the model on an NVIDIA Titan RTX GPU-equipped computer.

To test the efficacy of the prompt engineering approach in the summarisation service, we experimented with two types of prompts; with context and without context. Prompts with context included additional information or requests provided by users. Prompts without context only included the actual system instructions, without any additional user instructions. Furthermore, we also experimented with two different system prompts. System Prompt 1 specified a more elaborate prompt with instructions to the LLM to be helpful. System Prompt 2 was more bare bones and only instructed the LLM to provide a summary. The two prompts used are shown below.

Table 4. Summarisation System Prompt 1

```
Provide a detailed summary of the following document
using the given context. Be as helpful as possible.

context: "{context}"
document: "{text}"
```

Table 5. Summarisation System Prompt

```
Summarise the provided document, using the supplied
context if provided.

context: "{context}"
document: "{text}"
```

A streamlit⁹ webapp (Fig. 1) was created to allow different users to upload their own datasets and experiment with providing various contexts. These contexts could also include instructions for the LLMs to tailor the summary that was generated. For example, it could include instructions to “focus only on transport related responses”, or “what do citizens say about bus services?”.

Summary Generator

The screenshot shows a web application titled "Summary Generator". It has a light blue header. Below the header, there is a text input field with the placeholder text "Provide any context you wish to. This is optional:". The input field contains the text "Focus on transportation related issues.". Below this, there is another text input field with the placeholder text "Provide a comments in an .xlsx file to summarise:". Below this field is a file upload area with a cloud icon and the text "Drag and drop file here" and "Limit 200MB per file • XLSX". To the right of this area is a "Browse files" button. Below the upload area, a file named "comment.xlsx" (29.6KB) is shown with a close button (X). Below the file list is a red "Submit" button. Below the submit button is a green success message: "Successfully generated the following summary.". Below this message is a detailed summary of transportation-related issues discussed by residents of Barton Hill area. The summary is titled "Public Transportation:" and lists two bullet points: "Many residents rely on buses to get to school or work, but they are dissatisfied with the current service, citing delays and unreliability." and "There is a need for more frequent and reliable bus services, particularly along Church Road."

Fig. 1. A Streamlit webapp created to experiment with different contexts.

For each prompt, 9 different contexts were devised. Therefore, including no context, there were 10 total summaries generated. The summaries were then ranked by domain experts as to their usefulness from 1 to 5; 1 being least useful and 5 being most useful. The results are discussed in Section 4.2. The contexts are shown in Table 6.

⁹ <https://streamlit.io/>

Table 6. Contexts supplied by domain experts.

ID	Context
1	No context
2	What do people think about bus services
3	What do people think about cycle lanes
4	Tell me about bike storage in the area
5	What do people like about their area
6	Tell me about green spaces
7	Tell me about air quality
8	What do people think about traffic
9	What do people think about anti-social behaviour
10	What is the biggest issue in the area

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Sentiment Analysis

The performance of our approach is reported in Table 7. In our evaluation of the Flan-T5 models, we focused on two key classification metrics, accuracy and F1-score, since they respectively provide an overview of the overall correctness, and the balance between precision and recall. The accuracy results demonstrate a clear progression as model size increases. The Flan-T5-large model performs significantly better, with 92% of its predictions being correct, and there is a notable jump in accuracy from the base to the large model, in line with the increase in model parameters. The F1 scores follow a similar trend, with all models showing high scores, hence a good balance between false positives and false negative errors made.

In terms of computational efficiency, we evaluated the model’s execution time on both CPU and GPU configurations. Running Flan-T5 with GPU acceleration results in roughly an 80% reduction in processing time compared to CPU execution. However, it is worth noticing that even with the larger model requiring >14 minutes for processing, this is still substantially faster than the time an analyst would spend classifying such data manually, which, according to staff members at Bristol City Council, could range from a couple of hours to days depending on the complexity and volume of the data.

For Flan-T5-large, by analysing the errors obtained, we see in particular that only one positive instance gets predicted as negative, and we have 34 false positives. Looking at these errors, we can notice that they occur mostly on statements that are not fully negative or positive in the sentiment spectrum, or where mixed feelings are present in the same statement. Table 8 shows some examples of these errors, where ‘True’

corresponds to the label selected by the respondent and simplified to binary form during our data preprocessing phase.

Table 7. Performance metrics for different Flan-T5 models

Model	Accuracy	F1-score	Time (CPU)	Time (GPU)
Flan-T5-small	0.81	0.88	1m43s	20s
Flan-T5-base	0.85	0.91	4m49s	50s
Flan-T5-large	0.92	0.95	14m15s	2m25s

Table 8. Some false positives and negatives results from Flan-T5-large

Statement	True	Predicted
There should be trees planted at this junction, there is plenty of space on the central island and wide footway. This would make the area look more pleasant and less industrial. They would also help absorb pollution.	Negative	Positive
Perfect place for diagonal pedestrian crossing please please please?! I can think of no better place for this in Bristol. So many stages to crossing this street. Phasing of lights should favour pedestrians and cyclists not cars.	Negative	Positive
The public rights of way on Troopers Hill need diverting to follow the existing paths, at the moment OS and other maps show routes that can't be followed.	Positive	Negative

This suggests that we need more nuance in our approach, perhaps by considering a bigger range of sentiments, or by analysing sentiments at sentence level or on different topics within each statement, rather than assigning a single sentiment to the full statement. Such an approach could better capture the complexity and potential ambiguity in responses, particularly those containing multiple, not binary, or conflicting sentiments.

Overall, these results are quite positive. The consistent improvement in both metrics as model size increases suggests that larger models do indeed capture more nuanced patterns in the data, leading to better classification performance. However, this comes at the cost of increased execution time. Despite this, the computational time remains significantly lower than what would be required for manual analysis, demonstrating the efficiency of automated approaches even with larger models.

4.2 Summarisation

For summarisation, we performed a domain expert evaluation. The results are shown in Fig. 2. The most useful summary was generated without any additional context for both system prompts (*Context 1*). However, there is a clear divergence between the two system prompts for all contexts after that. Overall, the scores of the summaries were inconsistent. For example, for *System Prompt 1*, *Contexts 5* and *8* were rated higher than other summaries. For *System Prompt 2*, the scores of the summaries were significantly lower. This seems to confirm the findings of Işıkdemir [9] that summaries are highly sensitive to the prompts. A simple instruction like ‘*to be more helpful*’ clearly improves the scores of the results, though the LLM appears unable to understand instructions to focus on specific topics or elements. Using a Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) based approach may help alleviate this issue [11].

Fig. 2. Human evaluated scores for different contexts and different system prompts.

5 Conclusion and future works

In this paper, we argued that Generative Artificial Intelligence (GAI), more specifically Large Language Models (LLMs) can be used for data analysis by public authorities. More specifically, we investigated sentiment analysis and summarization using open-source LLM models and applied them to survey data from the East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood case study. The results show that larger versions of LLMs consistently improve accuracy in sentiment classification tasks. As model size increased, performance metrics showed steady improvements, indicating better capture of nuanced patterns. However, this came with longer execution times, although remaining more efficient than manual analysis. Summarisation quality varied significantly based on the prompts used: explicit instructions produced better summaries, while additional context did not consistently improve results, according to experts’ evaluation.

We anticipate that such GAI-based services can provide efficient means to public authorities in performing data analysis and evaluating or assessing public opinion. These systems can process diverse data sources, including social media, comments on planning applications, petitions, etc. However, further research is needed to improve the accuracy of sentiment classification and summarisation of survey data. Our future work will focus on comparing LLMs with conventional models across these diverse data sources to understand their relative strengths and weaknesses. We plan to evaluate various LLMs for task-specific suitability, and explore prompt engineering techniques to optimise performance. For sentiment classification, we aim to implement Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA) to understand more nuanced patterns, and provide insights into both emotions and topics within the text. Regarding summarisation tasks, we intend to incorporate Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) techniques to improve contextual relevance by implementing pre-filtering of responses before inputting to the LLM for summarisation. Additionally, we will investigate how biases inherent in the training data of LLMs can impact the results and performance of the models, as understanding these biases helps in ensuring fair and accurate results.

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¹⁰ The GREENGAGE project - <https://www.greengage-project.eu/>

References

1. Bassoo, V., Ramnarain-Seetohul, V., Hurbungs, V., Fowdur, T.P., Beecharry, Y.: *Big Data Analytics for Smart Cities*, pp. 359–379. Springer International Publishing, Cham (2018). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-60435-0_15
2. Basyal, L., Sanghvi, M.: Text summarization using large language models: A comparative study of mpt-7b-instruct, falcon-7b-instruct, and openai chat-gpt models (2023), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.10449>
3. Chang, M.W., Ratinov, L., Roth, D., Srikumar, V.: Importance of semantic representation: Dataless classification. In: *Proceedings of the National Conference on Artificial Intelligence*. vol. 2, pp. 830–835 (2008)
4. Chung, H.W., Hou, L., Longpre, S., Zoph, B., Tay, Y., Fedus, W., Li, Y., Wang, X., Dehghani, M., Brahma, S., Webson, A., Gu, S.S., Dai, Z., Suzgun, M., Chen, X., Chowdhery, A., Castro-Ros, A., Pellat, M., Robinson, K., Valter, D., Narang, S., Mishra, G., Yu, A., Zhao, V., Huang, Y., Dai, A., Yu, H., Petrov, S., Chi, E.H., Dean, J., Devlin, J., Roberts, A., Zhou, D., Le, Q.V., Wei, J.: Scaling instruction-finetuned language models. *Journal of Machine Learning Research* 25(70), 1–53 (2024), <http://jmlr.org/papers/v25/23-0870.html>
5. Covato, E., Jeawak, S.: Understanding People’s Perceptions of Their Liveable Neighbourhoods: A Case Study of East Bristol. In: *12th International Conference on Geographic Information Science (GIScience 2023)*. Leibniz International Proceedings in Informatics (LIPIcs), vol. 277, pp. 24:1–24:6 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.4230/LIPIcs.GIScience.2023.24>
6. Davies, S.R., Selin, C., Gano, G., Ângela Guimarães Pereira: Citizen engagement and urban change: Three case studies of material deliberation. *Cities* 29(6), 351–357 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2011.11.012>
7. Davoodian, Z., Mohebi, A.: Unveiling sentiment insights in smart cities: Exploring the role of social media. In: *2024 8th International Conference on Smart Cities, Internet of Things and Applications (SCIoT)*. pp. 68–75 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1109/SCIoT62588.2024.10570117>
8. Halfpenny, P.: The analysis of qualitative data. *The Sociological Review* 27(4), 799–827 (1979)
9. Işıkdemir, Y.E.: NLP transformers: Analysis of LLMs and traditional approaches for enhanced text summarization. *Eskişehir Osmangazi Üniversitesi Mühendislik ve Mimarlık Fakültesi Dergisi* 32(1), 1140–1151 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.31796/ogummf.1303569>
10. Izzidien, A., Sargeant, H., Steffek, F.: LLM vs. Lawyers: Identifying a Subset of Summary Judgments in a Large UK Case Law Dataset (Mar 2024). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2403.04791>
11. Jeong, C.: Generative AI service implementation using LLM application architecture based on RAG model and LangChain framework. *Journal of Intelligence and Information Systems* 29(4), 129–164 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.13088/jiis.2023.29.4.129>
12. Khan, Z., Ludlow, D., Loibl, W., Soomro, K.: Ict enabled participatory urban planning and policy development. *Transforming Government: People, Process and Policy* 8(2), 205–229 (Jan 2014). <https://doi.org/10.1108/TG-09-2013-0030>
13. Krugmann, J.O., Hartmann, J.: Sentiment analysis in the age of generative ai. *Customer Needs and Solutions* 11(1), 3 (Mar 2024). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40547-024-00143-4>

14. Liu, P., Yuan, W., Fu, J., Jiang, Z., Hayashi, H., Neubig, G.: Pre-train, prompt, and predict: A systematic survey of prompting methods in natural language processing. *ACM Comput. Surv.* 55(9) (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3560815>
15. Mohammadi, M., Al-Fuqaha, A., Sorour, S., Guizani, M.: Deep learning for iot big data and streaming analytics: A survey. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials* 20(4), 2923–2960 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1109/COMST.2018.2844341>
16. Naveed, H., Khan, A.U., Qiu, S., Saqib, M., Anwar, S., Usman, M., Akhtar, N., Barnes, N., Mian, A.: A comprehensive overview of large language models (2024), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2307.06435>
17. Orlanski, G.: Evaluating prompts across multiple choice tasks in a zero-shot setting (2022), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2203.15754>
18. Poplin, A.: Playful public participation in urban planning: A case study for on-line serious games. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems* 36(3), 195–206 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2011.10.003>
19. Rasheed, Z., Waseem, M., Ahmad, A., Kemell, K.K., Xiaofeng, W., Duc, A.N., Abrahamsson, P.: Can large language models serve as data analysts? a multi-agent assisted approach for qualitative data analysis (2024), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2402.01386>
20. Sarker, I.H.: Machine learning: Algorithms, real-world applications and research directions (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42979-021-00592-x>
21. Sharma, N.A., Ali, A.B.M.S., Kabir, M.A.: A review of sentiment analysis: tasks, applications, and deep learning techniques. *International Journal of Data Science and Analysis* (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41060-024-00594-x>
22. Soomro, K., Bhutta, M.N.M., Khan, Z., Tahir, M.A.: Smart city big data analytics: An advanced review. *WIREs Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery* 9(5), e1319 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1002/widm.1319>
23. Tai, R.H., Bentley, L.R., Xia, X., Sitt, J.M., Fankhauser, S.C., Chicas-Mosier, A.M., Monteith, B.G.: An examination of the use of large language models to aid analysis of textual data. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods* 23, 16094069241231168 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1177/16094069241231168>
24. Wang, Z., Pang, Y., Lin, Y.: Large language models are zero-shot text classifiers (2023), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2312.01044>
25. Xiao, Z., Yuan, X., Liao, Q.V., Abdelghani, R., Oudeyer, P.Y.: Supporting qualitative analysis with large language models: Combining codebook with gpt-3 for deductive coding. In: *Companion Proceedings of the 28th International Conference on Intelligent User Interfaces*. p. 75–78. IUI '23 Companion, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3581754.3584136>
26. Zaouali, K., Rekik, R., Bouallegue, R.: Deep learning forecasting based on auto-lstm model for home solar power systems. In: *2018 IEEE 20th International Conference on High Performance Computing and Communications; IEEE 16th International Conference on Smart City; IEEE 4th International Conference on Data Science and Systems (HPCC/SmartCity/DSS)*. pp. 235–242 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1109/HPCC/SmartCity/DSS.2018.00062>
27. Zhang, T., Ladhak, F., Durmus, E., Liang, P., McKeown, K., Hashimoto, T.B.: Benchmarking Large Language Models for News Summarization. *Transactions of the Association for Computational Linguistics* 12, 39–57 (01 2024). https://doi.org/10.1162/tacl_a_00632
28. Zhang, W., Deng, Y., Liu, B., Pan, S.J., Bing, L.: Sentiment analysis in the era of large language models: A reality check (2023), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2305.15005>